

INNOVATIVE PEDAGOGICAL MODEL OF DEVELOPMENT OF ARTISTIC-CREATIVE COMPETENCE OF FUTURE MUSIC TEACHERS ON THE BASIS OF ARTPEDAGOGICAL APPROACH

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7880424>

Abstract. *This article describes an innovative pedagogical model of developing the artistic and creative competence of future music education teachers based on the art-pedagogical approach. Also, this sample model project talks about the psycho-physiological characteristics, artistic-creative abilities, mental-intellectual thinking formation and development conditions of the future teacher in the process of professional training.*

Key words: *art pedagogy, model, artistic and creative competence, creative thinking, educational technologies, pedagogical methods.*

INTRODUCTION

One of the leading directions of modern education is the need to integrate and enrich pedagogical knowledge with the achievements of other disciplines. In the world, creative models of pedagogical processes aimed at developing the professional competence of future teachers are being applied to the educational process. In such conditions, we need to urgently reform the system of education and development, increase the thinking of the younger generation, introduce modern and effective technological education, develop the intellectual potential of the mind, and the physical capabilities of the whole. Developing the self-pedagogical system of developing the content of the flexibility, mobility, and axiological attitude of future teachers to pedagogical innovations, developing the creative thinking of students by creating a creative educational environment in pedagogical higher education institutions, future music education teachers improvement of the didactic mechanism of continuous development based on personal and professional competence and acmeological approaches is gaining urgent importance. In this process, special emphasis is placed on using the opportunities of music education and developing the artistic and creative competence of future teachers. Therefore, new approaches are being formed regarding the task of reforming music education and popularizing its high artistic and creative potential, forming and educating the members of society. For this, first of all, there is a need to reform the system of music teacher training, to use modern educational tools in the development of their artistic and creative competence.

Increasing the level of scientific-theoretical, pedagogical-psychological and scientific-methodical training of future music teachers in developed scientific research institutes and centers of the world, developing their personal, professional, and creative observation capabilities while training competitive pedagogic personnel in accordance with international qualification requirements, Many scientific-pedagogical studies aimed at introducing the competence approach to the educational process are being carried out. Important conclusions on the development of the professional competence, artistic ability, creative thinking and system of views of future music education teachers are being developed in these studies.

Nevertheless, in modern conditions, local education is experiencing a serious crisis, its depth and threatening nature:

A sharp decline in the culture of adults, teenagers and children of the population of Uzbekistan; the orientation of a significant part of today's youth to the pragmatic-utilitarian western model of life, the destruction of national culture, values and traditions, and the decrease of interest in them, despite the weight of decrees and laws being put into practice;

increasing conflict between generations living in the territory of our country; the incompatibility of the educational worldview of the generations whose worldviews were formed in two conflicting state systems in one century; devaluation of moral, cultural, and spiritual values in the minds of the young generation, increasing desire for wealth, entertainment, stereotype of living one day at a time, impunity;

destruction of the boundaries of the pedagogical "safety zone"; Violation of the principles and norms of behavior, aggression, drug addiction, an increase in juvenile delinquency; a conscious desire for a strict stratification of children in society according to their mental characteristics, the material wealth of their parents, etc.;

The indicators reflect the lack of a single (or similar in terms of methodological and content-related) approach to the issues of educating the young generation, and the increasing recognition of form rather than quality.

"Further improvement of the continuing education system, continuing the policy of training highly qualified personnel in line with the modern needs of the labor market" [1] pedagogy plays an important role in the training of future music education teachers in higher educational institutions. Therefore, on the basis of the art-pedagogical approach, special emphasis should be placed on the development of artistic and creative competence of future teachers of music education, the formation of artistic and creative taste and thinking, a new attitude to music as a national and creative value, the development of approaches remains one of the important tasks facing research work.

In the new development strategy of Uzbekistan, reforming higher music education, improving the quality of personnel training and forming professional competencies in them, as well as developing the system of artistic and creative thinking and ideals, and thereby having a positive effect on the education of students and youth, the tasks of achieving the effectiveness of acquired knowledge through a creative approach, developing their valuable attitude to art, developing their aesthetic taste, emotional impact and especially musical thinking are gaining relevance. Therefore, based on the development of artistic and creative competence of future teachers of music education, they should be able to educate them through aesthetic taste, artistic imaginative imagination, creativity, initiative, free thinking, creative approach, informal debates and music education, it is necessary to improve the pedagogical methodology-technology that develops skills. For this, one of the important tasks is to organize education on the basis of innovative approaches that allow to develop the artistic and creative competence of future music teachers, and to organize a pedagogical process aimed at integrating educational methods. Sh. Mirziyoyev, the leader of our state, "an urgent issue that always worries and worries us - manners, behavior, cultural level of our youth, in a word, is connected with their upbringing"[2;452] to pay serious attention to a number of issues in order to conduct a large work in this direction and further enhance its effectiveness.

Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 28, 2022 "On the development strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026" No. PF-60, 2022. The implementation of the activities of the Ministries of Higher Education, Science and Innovation, which was announced in the President's address to the Oliy Majlis in December, PF-5847 of October 8, 2019 "Approving the concept of the development of the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030" Decree No. PQ-3775 dated June 5, 2018 "Additional measures to increase the quality of education in higher education institutions and ensure their active participation in comprehensive reforms implemented in the country" on" Decree No. PF-6097 dated October 29, 2020 "On Approving the Concept of Development of the Higher Education System until 2030", PQ-2909 No. "Higher Education" dated April 20, 2017 on measures to further develop the education system", PQ-3775 dated June 5, 2018 "On improving the quality of education in higher education institutions and ensuring their active participation in comprehensive reforms implemented in the country on additional measures", dated February 27, 2020 No. PQ-4623 "On measures to further improve the field of pedagogical education", dated May 26, 2020 "Culture and art This research work serves to a certain extent in the implementation of the tasks defined in the Decree No. PF-6000 "On measures to further increase the role and influence of the horse industry in the life of society" and other regulatory legal documents.

METODOLOGY

The level of study of this research work on the development of artistic competence of future music education teachers and the formation of a valuable attitude to art is divided into three parts - studies in Western countries, the CIS and Uzbekistan can be.

The educational functions of music education in Western countries, the role of oriental melodies in the education of a person and the development of musical thinking have been studied by scientists such as D. Karomatli, T. Levin, Y. Elsner and A. Yunglar.

According to E.B.Abdulin, Yu.B.Aliyev, O.A.Apraksina, L.G.Archajnikova, D.B.Kabalevsky, N.A.Kerentieva, L.V.Shkolyar, G.M.Zinin and other researchers from the scientists of the Commonwealth of Independent States, every specialist-musician has intelligence, high culture, innovation should have a set of personal and professional qualities, such as the ability to create, fulfill the educational mission, and the ability to identify the natural potential of a person.

O'zbekistonda ham musiqa ta'limini rivojlantirish, o'quvchi-yoshlarni ijodkorlik qobiliyatini shakllantirish, badiiy-ijodiy imkoniyatlarini rivojlantirish muammolari bilan M.Axmedov, H.Ahmedova, Sh.Janaydarov, F.Jo'rayev, S.Yo'ldosheva, D.Kamolova, A.Mahammatov, B.Mustafojev, H.Nurmatov, I.Razzoqov, D.Ro'ziyev, O.Safarov, J.Yarashev, N.Qiyomov, M.Qosimova, Scientists such as I. Kudratov, A. Koshayev and A. Hasanov were involved. Also, along with the scientific researches of the scientists who theoretically analyzed the musical heritage and its historical-philosophical roots and place in the people's spirituality, G.Matyokubova, F.Askar, I.A.Ganiyeva, G.A.Tursunova, Z.Oripov, Sh.I.Aykhodjayeva, M. Qalandarova's research works can be included.

M. Akhmedov, H. Ahmedova, Sh. Janaydarov, F. Jo'rayev, S. Yoldasheva, with the problems of developing music education, forming the creativity of students and youth, and developing their artistic and creative potential. D.Kamolova, A.Mahammatov, B.Mustafojev, H.Nurmatov, I.Razzokov, D.Roziyev, O.Safarov, J.Yarashev, N.Kiyomov, M.Kasimova, Scientists such as I. Kudratov, A. Koshayev and A. Hasanov were involved.

However, the fact that the innovative pedagogical foundations of the development of artistic and creative competence of future music education teachers based on the art-pedagogical approach of the above-mentioned scientists were not specifically studied increases the importance of the research work provided in this article.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Russian pedagogue V.N. Shatskaya stated that aesthetic education is aimed at developing a sense of beauty in students. According to V.A. Sukhomlinsky, he recognized that moral and aesthetic education is one of the most necessary tasks of school education. He was convinced of the importance of teaching to see and perceive beauty in personality education.

B. T. Likhachyov pays special attention to the practical side of the issue. He developed a unique approach to the use of art objects as a means of aesthetic education. The teacher distinguishes three main stages of this process:

- Students' direct perception of the artistic work;
- In the student's activity, he practically repeats the impression he got from the work of art;
- Analysis of the completed task;

Lessons organized on the basis of an art-pedagogical approach develop the following qualities in a student:

<h1>Possibilities of art pedagogy</h1>		
<p>Ideas of Humanism:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - the concept of beauty; - harmony; - good and evil 	<p>Aesthetic education:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - the student's desire for the creative process; - development of creativity; - creativity; 	<p>Reflection Ideas:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - thinking; - analysis; - attention to problematic questions; - solving non-standard tasks; - quick adaptation to changing situations; - ability to quickly accept new situations; - openness to new ideas and points of view;

- Humanistic ideas - the teacher should have an artistic and creative influence on students, using his skills and experience. It implies the need to give priority to the formation of beauty, harmony, good, evil and other concepts in them.

- Focusing on the creation of creative activities that are important in the context of aesthetic education. The teacher performs the task of creating conditions that reveal the student's inner experiences and stimulate the process of his creative activity. It should be noted that the use of visual arts, music, literature, dance and other branches of science in art pedagogy is the basis for creating this mental-psycho-emotional environment.

- the idea of integrativeness is based on the interaction of art, psychology and pedagogy, taking into account that a harmonious combination of various methods of organizing artistic and creative activity has been established, the moral and artistic development of the student's personality the development of creative competences is encouraged.

- the idea of reflection is of great importance for aesthetic education, and its basis is to train the student to think, analyze, pay attention to problematic issues, solve non-standard problems, quickly adapt to difficult situations, sufficiently perceive new views and values, as well as , forms characteristics such as openness to new ideas. This approach is a holistic system of combining various forms of artistic and creative activities of students, aimed at stimulating the processes of meaning formation, understanding it and creating the necessary conditions [3,202].

CONCLUSION

The importance of art pedagogy in the modern educational space is undoubtedly relevant. The goal of art pedagogy is to improve the professional preparation of future teachers based on the unity of logical-epistemological and emotional-creative components. The gradual orientation of the educational process to the principles and essence of art pedagogy has already begun in the higher educational institutions and schools of the MDX, which will undoubtedly start a new stage in the development of education [4,49].

The theoretical analysis of the main categories of this study showed that in the conditions of modern higher education, not only having a set of knowledge, skills and abilities, but also having a high level of structural qualification, even returning to a new type of specialization is expressed in the personal changes that occurred in the process of directed education.

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